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Maydis Stigma (Corn Silk) Extract Protects the Functionality and Histoarchitecture of the Testis against Paraquat Induced Toxicity

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Abstract

Paraquat is a widely used herbicide and is toxic to humans. This study investigated the therapeutic potentials of ethanolic extract of Maydis stigma in reversing paraquat induced testicular toxicity in animal models. Thirty-five male Wistar rats were divided into control and six test groups (n=5). Control group (A) received feed and distilled water, while other groups (B-G) were treated daily and orally for 4 weeks as follows; group B (20mg/kg b.w. of paraquat); group C (1000mg/kg b.w. of ethanolic extract of Maydis stigma): group D (co-administration of 20mg/kg b.w. of paraquat and 500mg/kg b.w. of ethanolic extract of Maydis stigma), group E (co-administration of 20mg/kg b.w. of paraquat and 1000mg/kg b.w. of ethanolic extract of Maydis stigma), group F (20mg/kg b.w. of paraquat for one week, followed subsequently by 500mg/kg b.w. of ethanolic extract of Maydis stigma daily for 3 weeks) and group G (20mg/kg b.w. of paraquat for only 1 week and fed for another 3 weeks). At the end, reproductive profiles such as sperm count, morphology and motility; serum testosterone levels and histomorphometric architecture of their testes were assessed. Results revealed that paraquat produced altered sperm profiles, induced necrosis, caused loss of sperm bundles and reduced organ weights and testosterone levels (p<0.05). However, treatment with Maydis stigma extract showed better sperm profiles including enhanced spermatogenesis and higher sera testosterone levels thereby conferring protective potentials against toxicity induced by paraquat. We therefore suggest from our findings that Maydis stigma acts in a dose dependent manner to ameliorate paraquat-induced toxicity effect in animal models.

Keywords: *Maydis stigma, paraquat, testis, male reproductive profile, histology*

INTRODUCTION

Paraquat (1,1'-Dimethyl 1-4, 4'-bipyridiniumdichloride) is a general contact herbicide.^[1] It is toxic to animals, producing free radicals in-vivo such as hydrogen peroxide and superoxide ion that cause severe damages in various organ.^[2, 3, 4, 5] In humans, paraquat exposure causes a variety of disease conditions and sexual disturbances.^[6, 7, 8] Testicular damage has also been reported to be associated with oral paraquat exposure.^[9] It is well documented that paraquat decreases the functionality of reproductive and accessory reproductive organs of animal causing decrease in spermatogenesis and inhibition of prolactin, follicle stimulating hormone, luteinizing hormone and testosterone production.^[10, 11, 12]

Herbal products have been used to produce ameliorative effects, protecting tissues from the injurious effects of reactive oxygen species.^[13] *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) possess large and varying amounts of bioactive components, such as flavonoids, polysaccharides, steroids, tannins, alkaloids, proteins and vitamins.^[14, 15, 16] It also possesses antioxidant, anti-depressant, antibacterial, anti-diabetic, anti- inflammation, diuretic, anti-fatigue,

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antifungal as well as anti-tumor properties.^[17, 18, 19 20] Despite all these beneficial activities, limited literature exist on the effect of ethanolic extract of corn silk on paraquat induced testicular damage, thus this study aimed at investigating the effect of ethanolic extracts of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) on paraquat exposed testis in adult male Wistar rats.

METHOD

Ethical Approval and Duration of Study

The ethical approval for this study was obtained from the ethical committee of the Faculty of Basic Medical Sciences, Nnamdi Azikiwe University before the commencement of this research. The experiment lasted for 4 weeks.

Animal Procurement and Treatment

To carry out this research, sixty (60) growing male Wistar rats (140-200g) were purchased and housed in well ventilated stainless-steel rat cages under room temperature (27– 31°C) and fed with standard rat feed and distilled water *ad libitum* for an acclimatization period of two weeks. The bedding of the cages was clean sawdust. The cages were cleaned every day to maintain a clean environment and prevent infection. After acclimatisation, we used a total of 25 of these Wistar rats to determining the Median lethal dose for both paraquat and ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk), while 35 of them were used for the experiment proper. The Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals was strictly followed.^[21]

Procurement and Preparation of Ethanolic Extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk).

Maydis Stigma (corn silk) were obtained from a local farm in Nnewi, Nnewi North Local Government Area of Anambra State during the harvest of matured corn curbs. The *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) collected was of the sweet corn (yellow su) variety (*Zea mays* convar. *saccharata* var. *rugosa*). They were washed in running water to remove dirt and shed dried. Afterwards, it was grinded using a local grinder into a coarse form. 250g of the grinded *Maydis Stigma* were soaked in 1000ml of absolute ethanol (BDH England) for 48 hours with intermittent shaking after which the mixture was sieved using porcelain cloth and was further filtered using Whatman No. 1 filter paper into a clean glass beaker. The filtrate was concentrated using digital rotatory evaporator (TT-S2 Techmel and Techmel USA) and was further dried using thermostat oven (DHG- 9023A Pecmedicals USA) at 45°C into a gelly-like substance which was stored in a refrigerator at 4 °C for further use.

Toxicity Test for Ethanolic Extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk).

The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) was determined using the method as described Lorke,^[22] with slight modifications. In this study which involved two phases, 13 rats were used. They received graded doses of the extract via oral route. LD₅₀ of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* was found to be above 5000mg/kg via oral route in adult male wistar rats.

Phytochemical analysis for ethanolic seed extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk)

We carried out the phytochemical screening for ethanolic seed extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) using the method as described by Okwu.^[23]

Procurement and Toxicity Test for Paraquat

Paraquat in the form of Paraquat Dichloride 276g/l (Springfield Agro LTD, Apapa, Lagos) was procured from the Agro-allied section of New Market Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. The median lethal dose (LD₅₀) for paraquat used was determined using the method as described by Lorke^[22] with slight modifications. In this toxicity study which involved two phases, 13 rats were also used. They received graded doses of paraquat via oral route. LD₅₀ of paraquat was found to be 50mg/kg via oral route in adult male wistar rats.

Experimental Design and Protocol

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After acclimatization and toxicity tests, 35 rats from the acclimatized group were weighed and divided into seven groups (A-G) of 5 animals each. Group A served as control and received only distilled water and feed *ad libitum* throughout the duration of the experiment. Group B received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 4 weeks. Group C received 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* for 4 weeks. Group D received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 500mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* for 4 weeks, while Group E received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* for 4 weeks. Group F received 20mg/kg of paraquat for one week after which the paraquat was withdrawn and 500mg/kg ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* (Corn silk) was administered daily for three weeks. Group G received 20mg/kg of paraquat for one week after which paraquat was withdrawn and rats left to feed for three weeks. Generally paraquat was administered twice a week (Mondays and Fridays) while all extracts were administered once daily depending on the duration. All administrations were done orally by carefully inserting a syringe with a cannula affix on it, into the oral cavity of the rat. Weights of experimental animals were measured twice a week. Concentration of paraquat used in this experiment was determined after close evaluation of several scholarly works.^[10, 24, 25]

Blood Samples Collection and Organ Extraction

This experiment lasted for 4 weeks. Twenty four hours after the last substrate administration, the rats were sedated using chloroform vapour. Blood samples were collected through ocular puncture into plain specimen bottles after which the sera were separated using a centrifuge and collected in well labelled plain blood specimen bottles and stored in a refrigerator for sera testosterone hormone assay.

Testosterone Assay

The sera samples we collected were assayed for testosterone levels using a Microwell enzyme linked immunoassay (ELISA) technique; using analytical grade agent (Syntron Bioresearch Inc., USA). Results obtained were documented and expressed in ng/ml.

Analysis of reproductive profiles

Following our experimental design, we used sperm parameters as a measure of the reproductive profile to evaluate the effect of the administration of paraquat and ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* on the testes of the animals used in this study. This process came immediately after the collection of blood samples for testosterone hormone assay. The right testes together with their epididymis were quickly dissected out of the sedated experimental animals after a midline abdominal incision. They were weighed after which the epididymis was carefully separated and the epididymal fluid collected from its caudal part and used to carryout analysis on sperm parameters, while the testes were fixed in freshly prepared Bouin's fluid for routine histological preparation. The sperm parameters assessed include sperm count, motility and morphology.

A. Sperm count:

Investigation on sperm count was carried out using the method as described by World Health Organization,^[26] with slight modifications.

Briefly, a graduated cylinder was used to dilute the epididymal fluid in sodium bicarbonate formalin diluting fluid in the proportion of 1 in 20. A Pasteur pipette was then used to transfer the dilution to an improved Neubauer ruled chamber and allowed to stand for 3-5 minutes. The 10× objective was used to view, with the condenser iris closed sufficiently to give good contrast, and the number of spermatozoa in 2 large squares (2 sq mm) counted. The number counted was multiplied by 10⁶.

B. Sperm Motility:

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Investigation on sperm motility was carried out using the method as described by World Health Organization,^[26] with slight modifications.

Briefly, a well-mixed drop of liquefied epididymal fluid obtained from the caudal end of the epididymis was placed on a slide, evenly distributed and covered with a cover slide. The 40x objective was used to observe and count. A total of 100 spermatozoa were counted out which the number of motile ones was recorded in percentage.

C. Sperm Morphology:

Investigation on sperm morphology was carried out using the method as described by World Health Organization,^[26] with slight modifications.

Briefly, a thin smear of liquefied well mixed epididymal fluid was made on a slide. While still wet, the smear was fixed with diluted 1:20 in 10% neutral buffered formalin and with the aid of light microscope at x400 magnification. The smear was counterstained with dilute (1 in 20) Loeffle's methylene blue for 2 minutes, and washed off with water. The smear was drained and allowed to air dry. The smear was examined for normal and abnormal spermatozoa using 40x objective. The 100x objective was used to confirm the abnormalities. A count of 100 spermatozoa was made and the percentage showing normal and abnormal morphology was deduced. In this study a spermatozoa was considered to be abnormal morphologically if it had one or more of the following features: rudimentary tail, round head and detached head and was expressed as a percentage of morphologically normal sperm.

Histological examination

This was carried out to observe changes in the histoarchitecture of the testes of the experimental animals used in this study following treatment with paraquat and the ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma*. After separating the epididymis from the testes and fixation of the testes in freshly prepared Bouin's fluid for routine histological preparation. The histological method of processing tissues for histopathological investigations involved the basic stapes for Haematoxylin and eosin staining (fixing, clearing, impregnation, cutting, and staining) and examination of histological slides for histological report.

Briefly, the testes from each rat were fixed in well labelled specimen bottles containing freshly prepared Bouin's solution. The fixed tissues were then dehydrated in ascending grades of alcohol to prevent distortion to cell structure which would have happened if directly placed in absolute alcohol. Clearing of these tissues was done by passing the tissues through 3 changes of xylene. Impregnation and infiltration of the tissues with molten paraffin wax was carried out to remove the clearing agent. Embedding was carried out using molten paraffin wax. On solidification, the tissue blocks were sectioned with the aid of a microtome (SKD-202A, China). Staining was done with haematoxylin and eosin dyes and were finally viewed under a light microscope (Olympus XS2-107BN, Japan) and photomicrographs obtained using a photomicroscope (Olympus, Japan).

Data Analysis

All data obtained from this study were analysed using SPSS version 23 software package. These data was analysed using one way ANOVA followed by Post HOC Fisher's LSD multiple comparison. Values were termed significant at $p \leq 0.05$.

RESULTS

Results we obtained after the various analysis showed that administration of paraquat had a deleterious effect on some parameters such as sera testosterone levels as well as sperm count, sperm motility and morphology. Relative testicular weight was also negatively affected. However, administration of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* produced results that showed protective and ameliorative effects.

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Effect of Co-Administration of Ethanolic Extracts of *Maydis Stigma* (Corn Silk) and Paraquat on the Body Weight

Results obtained following body weight analysis showed a general increase in body weights of all experimental groups irrespective of the substrate they received as shown in tables 1 and 2.

Table 1: Effect of co-administration of ethanolic extracts of corn silk (*maydis stigma*) and paraquat on Body weight of Adult Wistar Rat

Group	Weight	MEAN±SD	Weight difference	p-Value	t-Value
Group A	Initial	135±17.32			
	Final	208.75±11.81	73.75	0.001	-7.035
Group B	Initial	130±20.00			
	Final	212.5±25.00	82.5	0.002	-5.154
Group C	Initial	162.5±9.57			
	Final	268.75±23.94	106.25	0.001	-8.243
Group D	Initial	127.5±34.03			
	Final	206.25±55.43	78.75	0.052	-2.421
Group E	Initial	160±16.32			
	Final	275±20.41	115	0.001	-8.799
Group F	Initial	122.5±12.58			
	Final	206.25±23.94	83.75	0.001	-6.194
Group G	Initial	97.5±113.24			
	Final	156.25±180.71	58.57	0.602	-0.551

Table 2: Comparison of Change in Body Weight

Group	Mean Weight Difference (g) Mean±SEM	F-value	p-value
Group A	73.72±2.12		
Group B	82.50±0.71		0.004
Group C	106.25±1.77		0.001
Group D	78.75±2.47	118.654	0.085
Group E	115.00±2.83		0.001
Group F	83.75±0.35		0.002
Group G	58.75±4.59		0.001

These tables (tables 1 and 2) shows that, there were increases in the body weights of all experimental groups. The highest weight gain was seen in Group E which was given 20mg/kg of paraquat and 1000m/kg ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma*, while the lowest weight gain was seen in Group G which was given only paraquat for 7days.

Effect of Co-Administration of Ethanolic Extracts of Corn Silk (*Maydis Stigma*) and Paraquat on Relative Testicular Weight.

Results obtained from analysis of relative testicular weight of the experimental animals showed that only the group that was administered paraquat alone for 4 weeks had a statistically lower relative testicular weight when compared to the Control as shown in table 3.

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Table 3: Effect of Co-Administration of Ethanolic Extracts of *Maydis Stigma* (Corn Silk) and Paraquat on Relative Testicular Weight of Adult Wistar Rat.

Group	Relative Testicular Weight (g) Mean±SEM	F-value	p-value
Group A	1.51±0.04		
Group B	0.80±0.22		0.008*
Group C	1.22±0.07		0.174
Group D	1.56±0.43	3.61	0.827
Group E	1.23±0.02		0.194
Group F	1.47±0.10		0.813
Group G	1.27±0.09		0.249

*= P<0.05

When compared with Group A, result obtained from this study showed that the relative testicular weight was significantly lower in Group B which received 20mg/kg of paraquat daily for 28days. There was however no significant difference in relative weight of testis between the control group and other experimental groups as represented in table 3.

Effect of Co-Administration of Ethanolic Extracts of Corn Silk (*Maydis Stigma*) and Paraquat on Reproductive parameters.

Figure 1: Effect of Co-Administration of Ethanolic Extracts of *Maydis Stigma* (Corn Silk) and Paraquat on testosterone levels (A) and sperm quality (sperm morphology (B), motility (C) and count (D)). (The animals are categorized as Group A: control: Group B: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 4 weeks; Group C: received 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* for 4 weeks. Group D: received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 500mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma*; Group E: received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma*; Group F: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 1 week and 500mg/kg ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* subsequently for 3weeks. Group G: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 1 week only. *=Statistically significant difference at p≤0.05).

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We analysed the data obtained from sera testosterone levels, sperm morphology, motility and count. The results (Fig 1A, B & D), collectively revealed statistically significant differences between the control and the test groups B, D, F and G, with these groups having significantly lower levels of serum testosterone, sperm motility and sperm count.

For sperm morphology (Fig 1C), statistically significant lower levels of normal sperm morphology were observed in groups B, D, and G. These groups showed a statistically significant difference from the control.

Test groups C, D, E, and F showed significantly higher mean values in all the parameters than group B. These observations show that the ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* had a dose dependent ameliorative effect on the testes.

Histopathological findings

Figure 2: Photomicrographs of the histology of rat testes showing the effect of co-administration of ethanolic extracts of *Maydis Stigma* (Corn Silk) and Paraquat. (A: control; Group B: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 4 weeks; Group C: received 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* for 4 weeks; Group D: received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 500mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma*; Group E: received a co-administration of 20mg/kg of paraquat and 1000mg/kg of ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma*; Group F: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 1 week and 500mg/kg ethanolic extract of *Maydis stigma* subsequently for 3weeks. Group G: received 20mg/kg of paraquat for 1 week only).

Histological slides of the testis we processed were viewed under a light microscope (Olympus XS2-107BN, Japan) as shown in figure 2. We observed that the control showed a normal testicular architecture lined with sertoli cell (SC) and well enhanced spermatogenesis (WES) (Fig 2A). In group B, there was severe arrest of spermatogenesis (SAS) and necrosis of both sertoli cells (SC) and interstitial cells of the Leydig (ICL) (Fig 2B). In groups C, D and E, we observed similar testicular histoarchitecture, with seminiferous tubules lined with Sertoli cell (SC) and well enhanced spermatogenesis (WES) (Figures 2C, 2D and 2E). For group F and G, we

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observed apparently normal seminiferous tubules lined with both sertoli cells (SC) and interstitial cells of the Leydig (ICL) (Figures 2F and 2G).

These observations indicate that oral paraquat exposure affected the testicular architecture, with reduced density of sperm bundles in the seminiferous tubules as well as the general thinning of the linings of these tubules indicating loss of spermatogonia, sertoli cells and interstitial cells of Leydig responsible for sperm production, nurturing and production of testosterone. However, the co-administration of paraquat with ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma* (Corn Silk) to a large extent provided a sort of shielding effect on the cells of the seminiferous tubule and sperm cells as the density of sperm bundles increased, as well as thickening of the walls of the seminiferous tubules due to the presence of more spermatogonia, sertoli cells and interstitial cells of Leydig.

Discussion

Male infertility remains a concern in reproductive biology, with a wide range of studies exploring options for a definitive diagnosis and treatment. There is still no clear cut treatment regimen to arrest this increasing problem. Conventional therapeutics employed in the management of male infertility include the use of testosterone and other injectable gonadotropin formulations. Interestingly, herbal products have been used to produce ameliorative effects, as many phytochemicals found in parts of plants have been documented to have beneficial health effects and used to effectively manage disease conditions ^[27, 9, 13] and to manufacture potent medications.^[28]

Paraquat is a general purpose herbicide which upon exposure to animals generates free radicals (reactive oxygen species) that cause cellular damage via lipid peroxidation, activation of NF- κ B, mitochondrial damage and apoptosis in many organs.^[29, 30, 31, 32, 33, 34] *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk), a rich but often discarded part of corn after harvest possess large and varying amounts of bioactive components, such as flavonoids, polysaccharides, steroids, tannins, alkaloids, proteins and vitamins.^[14, 15, 16] It has been successfully used as antioxidants^[17, 35] and employed in the management of kidney and prostate conditions.^[35]

In our study which investigated the therapeutic potentials of the ethanolic extracts of *Maydis stigma* in reversing paraquat induced testicular toxicity in rat model, we observed a general increase in body weights of all experimental groups irrespective of the substrate they received. However, relative testicular weight of the experimental animals that received paraquat alone for 4 weeks was statistically lower when compared to the Control. Sera testosterone levels were significantly lower in experimental animals that received paraquat alone and also in those that received paraquat in combination with 500mg/kg body weight of ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma* when compared to Control. Sperm motility and sperm counts were lower ($p \leq 0.05$) in test groups B, D, F and G when compared with Control. Percentage of normal sperm (morphology) was also significantly lower in groups B, D, and G when compared to Control. Histopathological investigations on the testes showed that paraquat when administered alone, reduced spermatogenesis via loss of sperm bundles, in addition to necrosis of the testicular tissues while an increase in the density of sperm bundles, thickened walls of the seminiferous tubules due to the presence of more spermatogonia, sertoli cells and interstitial cells of Leydig was observed following the co-administration of paraquat with ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma*. This indicates a protective effect on the cells of the seminiferous tubule and sperm cells.

The reduction in sera testosterone levels, sperm count, cellular damage and the necrosis induced by paraquat exposure could have resulted from the induction of oxidative stress on the testicular tissues by paraquat.^[9, 10] Paraquat undergoes redox cycling in-vivo, and is reduced by an electron donor such as NADPH before being oxidized by an electron receptor such as dioxygen to produce superoxide (eg. hydrogen peroxide), a major reactive oxygen species (ROS) which are highly toxic.^[30] Paraquat impacts tissue biomolecules such as proteins, lipids, lipoproteins and DNA which significantly causes the reduction of biochemical activities such as hormone production, alteration of cellular membrane and induction of apoptosis.^[36] The apoptosis of cells and tissues was evidenced in this research by the thinning of the cell walls of the seminiferous tubules indicating the loss of

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cellular linings. Thinning of the wall of the seminiferous tubules and consequent loss of supporting cells such as sertoli cells and Leydig cells upon oral exposure to paraquat as we observed in our study further indicates the deleterious nature of paraquat on the testis. Loss of Leydig cells leads to diminished secretion of testosterone. This diminished secretion of testosterone generally leads to reduced fertility.^[37, 38, 39] Significantly lower relative testicular weight we observed in the group that received only paraquat alone could be a direct consequence of the thinning of the walls of the seminiferous tubules and loss of sperm bundles visible in the histology slide of their testes. This really supports the categorization of paraquat as an anti-fertility agent and contact with the body especially via oral route should be avoided.

Soothing effect of *Maydis stigma* was evidenced in this research. *Maydis Stigma* contain antioxidants which have the ability to prevent and ameliorate oxidation reactions in tissues.^[40, 41] It has been documented that consumption of *Maydis Stigma* extract induces a dose dependent protein expression of Nrf2 (a transcription factor) and detoxifying antioxidant enzymes such as glutathione reductase (GR) and superoxide dismutase (SOD).^[42] Nrf2 (a transcription factor) binds to the antioxidant response element in a number of target genes which encode for many of these enzymes like GR and SOD.^[42] The protein products of these genes do provide protection against oxidative stress. SOD produced is responsible for ROS metabolizing activity and catalyzes the neutralization of superoxide anion and hydrogen peroxide. In addition, glutathione reductase (GR) helps in keeping the balance of glutathione (GSH) and glutathione disulfide (GSDS),^[43] a natural tissue antioxidants and a product of reduction of peroxides such as hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and organic hydroperoxides (ROOH) respectively).^[44]

Maydis Stigma is also rich in calcium, magnesium, iron, zinc, manganese, and copper.^[45, 46, 47] Zinc is an important component of numerous metalloenzymes and metalloproteins,^[48] and is also involved in immune function,^[49] cell growth and proliferation,^[50] as well as DNA replication and transcription.^[51] In addition, zinc is vital in reproduction as it is essential in germ cell development.^[52] Zinc also possess antioxidant properties,^[53] carrying out this process via mechanisms which includes synthesizing metallothionein, that inhibits the production of free radicals;^[54] functioning as a structural and catalytic component of superoxide dismutase (SOD), which ameliorates the toxicity of reactive oxygen species via catalyzing the dismutation of O₂⁻ into H₂O₂ and O₂.^[55] and also preventing oxidation by binding to sulfhydryl (SH) groups in cell membrane proteins by blocking the binding sites of iron and copper, which are pro-oxidants.^[53] These vital roles could be behind the significantly higher levels of sperm parameters and sera testosterone we observed in all experimental groups that received graded doses of *Maydis Stigma* extract when compared to the group that received daily doses of paraquat alone for 4 weeks. Similar roles of zinc in improving sperm production has been documented by Michele *et al*,^[56] Uz *et al*^[57] and Abbasi *et al*.^[58]

In addition to the actions of zinc and other phytochemicals discussed, *Maydis Stigma* contains some trace elements such as calcium and magnesium that are equally vital and play significant roles in aiding and maintaining the production of mature sperm.^[45, 46, 47] Clinical examinations in humans have shown that calcium and magnesium levels are decreased in infertile men compared to fertile men.^[59, 60, 61] These minerals are present in corn silk extracts could have complimented the pro-fertility ability of other bioactive components found in corn silk.

The assertion from our observation is that *Maydis Stigma* extract could confer some degree of protection on testicular tissues and provide a window for tissue recovery thus the improvement in sperm count, morphology, motility and testosterone levels we observed.

Conclusion

The result of this study shows that ethanolic extract of *Maydis Stigma* (corn silk) exhibited dose dependent ameliorative effects on the testes of male wistar rats following co-administration with paraquat, a pesticide that causes testicular toxicity. This suggests that *Maydis Stigma* commonly discarded as waste during harvesting

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and processing of mature corn has a great medicinal potential if deployed to manage testicular toxicities arising from reactive oxygen species induced stress and should be promptly harnessed.

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